

Synthetic applications of 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of azomethine ylides and use in molecular nanotechnology[†]

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Manuscript received 20 February 2014, accepted 05 March 2014

Abstract : The 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions of azomethine ylides occupy a unique position in the synthesis of pyrrolidines – an important building block for the synthesis of many natural products and pharmaceuticals. An overview of the work reported from our group along with current trends is described.

Keywords : 1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition reaction, azomethine ylides, spiro bridgehead bicyclic heterocycles, DFT calculations and stereoselectivity.

Introduction

1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition (DC) (Huisgen Cycloaddition)¹ is a general and extremely effective route for the synthesis of a great variety of heterocyclic systems, with laboratory, industrial or pharmacological applications. The heterocyclic derivatives thus constructed provide complex functionalized framework of organic molecules in which many functional groups are masked in a protected form². The general reaction is depicted in Scheme 1 allowing the presence of many functional groups in both components, namely 1,3-dipoles and dipolarophiles (alkenes or alkynes).

Scheme 1. General 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions.

The available precursors for a dipole can be basically divided into two groups : the allyl anion-type such as nitrones, azomethine ylides, azomethine imines, carbonyl ylides and carbonyl imines, and the linear propargyl/allenyl anion-type such as nitrile oxides, nitrile imines, nitrile ylides, diazoalkanes and azides (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Important 1,3-dipoles in the synthesis of heterocycles.

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

The [2s+4s] addition is stereoconservative (suprafacial) and stereospecific, and the six π -electrons participate in a concerted or non-concerted reaction pathway controlled by the HOMO-LUMO interaction rules^{3,4}. This elevated stereocontrol is responsible for the high diastereo- and regioselectivity achieved in a number of heterocycles⁵. Another important feature^{6,7} is that up to four stereogenic centres can be unambiguously generated in a single step irrespective of diastereo- or enantioselective approach performed. According to Sustman⁸ the 1,3-DC reactions have been classified into three types depending upon the relative FMO energies between the dipole and dipolarophile (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Classification of 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions showing different regiochemical orbital control.

Type I : HOMO controlled i.e. the interaction of $\text{HOMO}_{\text{dipole}}$ with $\text{LUMO}_{\text{dipolarophile}}$ is greatest.

Type II : HOMO, LUMO controlled i.e. both frontier orbital interactions are large.

Type III : LUMO controlled i.e. the interaction of $\text{LUMO}_{\text{dipole}}$ and $\text{HOMO}_{\text{dipolarophile}}$ is greatest.

Methods for generating azomethine ylides

Many methods for the formation of azomethine ylides have been developed, of which the most common is the reaction of an α -dione with an α -amino acid to form an iminium species, followed by the generation of carbanion^{9,10}. The *in situ* prepared azomethine ylides are subjected instantly to the cycloaddition reaction (Scheme 2). Other methods which have been exploited for synthesis of azomethine ylides (amy) are : deprotonation of iminium salts¹¹, isomerization of an imine derivative of α -aminoester¹², intramolecular *N*-alkylation/demethylation cascade¹³, conrotatory bond cleavage¹⁴ and reaction of acetophenone with thiopyridine¹⁵. Some examples of 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction of amy's. Some illustrative examples are cited below :

1,3-Dipolar cycloadditions of azomethine ylides

(i) Recently Gryko *et al.*¹⁶ have revealed the unre-

cedented reactivity of naphthalene bisimides as dipolarophiles in 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition with *in situ* formed azomethine ylides (Scheme 3).

(ii) Yie Yu and group¹⁷ have described a bisphosphoric acid catalyzed 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of buta-2,3-dienoates with azomethine ylides yielding 3-methylenepyrrolidine derivatives (**3**) with excellent enantioselectivity upto 97% (Scheme 4).

(iii) James M. Longmire and coworkers¹⁸ have screened a highly reactive Ag^{I} catalyzed [3+2] cycloaddition of azomethine ylides using silver acetate as the catalytic precursor and chiral phosphine ligands to produce proline derivatives (Scheme 5).

Scheme 2

(iv) Bor-Cherng Hong and associates¹⁹ have reported the cycloaddition of cinnamaldehyde derivatives (**6**, **7**) with proline to produce corresponding hexahydro-1*H*-pyrrolizine (**8** and **9**) (Scheme 6).

(v) Boa *et al.*²⁰ have synthesized pyrrole derivatives

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Scheme 3

tion of amy's and their 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions, some of the examples are summarized below :

(i) The reaction of acenaphthylene-1,2-dione (12) with chiral cyclic secondary α -amino acids *viz.* L-proline (13a) and thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid (13b) gave rise to the intermediate azomethine ylide (14) which has been trapped by acetylenic and ethylenic dipolarophiles to produce bridgehead bicyclic cycloadducts in 75–85% yield^{21,22} (Scheme 8).

Scheme 4

Scheme 5

Scheme 6

(10, 11) of benzo[*b*]thiophene-1,1-dioxide with stabilized and non-stabilized azomethine ylides in low and high yield with low stereoselectivity (Scheme 7).

Over the past 15 years, in our laboratory, we have also exponentially exploited this method for the genera-

Scheme 7

Scheme 8

(ii) 1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition of azomethine ylide derived from 5-methylbenzo[*b*]thiophene-2,3-dione (17) with L-proline (13a) and thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid (13b) with various electron deficient dipolarophiles lead to the formation of novel spiroheterocycles having two or more chiral centres in 63–75% yield (Scheme 9).

(iii) Cycloaddition reaction of azomethine ylides generated by a decarboxylative route from 5-methylbenzo[*b*]thiophene (17) and piperidine-2-carboxylic acid (22) with different acetylenic and ethylenic dipolarophiles produced azabicycloadducts (24, 25) in 68–76% yield²³ (Scheme 10).

Scheme 9

Scheme 10

(iv) The reaction of indol-2,3-dione derivatives with (*R*)-(-)-thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid, afforded a thiazolo-oxazolidinone as the main product. When the reaction was carried out in the presence of a dipolarophile, 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition to the intermediate azomethine ylide lead to a novel spiro compounds (**27**)^{24,25} (Scheme 11).

Scheme 11

(v) The reaction of thioisatin with thiazolidine-2-carboxylic acid, afforded thiazolo-oxazolidinone as the main product. However when the reaction was carried out in the presence of a dipolarophile, 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition to the intermediate azomethine ylide lead to a diastereomeric mixture of *cis-trans* isomers (**33**, **34**)²⁶ (Scheme 12).

Scheme 12

Theoretical studies on 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of azomethine ylides

On the theoretical front also the 1,3-dipolar cycloadd-

dition reactions have evoked much interest over the past two decades^{27,28}. In order to investigate the stereo- and regio-selectivity of the cycloaddition reactions of azomethine ylides with various dipolarophiles reported above, an extensive DFT molecular orbital calculations have been carried out on Gaussian 03²⁹ suits of program

in our research group and following conclusions have been drawn :

The molecular geometry of the azomethine ylide derived from thioisatin and thiazolidine-2-carboxylic acid has been optimized on Gaussian 03 program. Geometry optimization showed that amy has almost planar structure. Instead of having an envelope shape the thiazolidine

ring is planar and lies in the same plane as that of the thioisatin ring. It may exist in two isomeric forms, one in which $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group and $\text{C}-\text{H}$ of the dipole are *syn* to

each other, 32_{syn} and the other in which these two groups are 32_{anti} (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Mode of attack of dipolarophile (diphenylacetylene) on amy 32 .

The transition state of the concerted 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions is usually controlled by frontier molecular orbitals of dipolarophiles and dipole (azomethine ylide). The favoured path involves $HOMO_{dipole}$ and $LUMO_{dipolarophile}$. It may be concluded that $HOMO_{dipole}$ and $LUMO_{dipolarophile}$ energy gap is lower than the $LUMO_{dipole}$ and $HOMO_{dipolarophile}$ gap and therefore the dominant FMO approach is $HOMO_{dipole} - LUMO_{dipolarophile}$. Both the HOMO and the LUMO of the dipole show uneven distribution of the electron density along the C-N-C dipole. In the HOMO case, the orbital coefficient is larger at C_1 (0.288) than at C_2 (-0.163). Similarly in the LUMO of methyl acrylate the atomic orbital coefficient are (0.611) and (-0.521) respectively (Fig. 4). Thus it may be concluded that there is better overlap when -COOMe group lies towards thioisatin ring, giving two possibilities $33a$ and $33b$. Out of these $33a$ is formed in diastereomeric excess probably due to the *endo* approach of -COOMe.

From the above discussions, it may be concluded that :

- (i) Geometry optimization of the azomethine ylide indicated that it has an almost planar structure.
- (ii) The azomethine ylide exists in two conformations *syn* and *anti*.
- (iii) The azomethine ylide is stabilized by the delocalization of dipolar charge into isatin, thioisatin and acenaphthacenedione nucleus.
- (iv) The dominant FMO approach is $HOMO_{dipole} - LUMO_{dipolarophile}$ as this energy gap is lower than the $LUMO_{dipole} - HOMO_{dipolarophile}$ gap.
- (v) The *endo* approach is favored as it results in the lower activation energy.

Atomic orbital coefficient of HOMO amy and LUMO methyl acrylate

Fig. 4. Possible isomers of cycloadduct 33 and its regioselectivity.

Fig. 5. Energy profile diagrams of azabicycloadduct 33 and 34 .

Use of 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition in molecular nanotechnology

Tagmatarchis and Prato³⁰ have carried out pioneering works on carbon nanotubes (CNT) *via* 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of azomethine ylides. CNT-based materials have been synthesized possessing differently functionalized solubilizing chains and hold strong promise as useful building blocks for the construction of novel hybrid for nano- and biotechnological applications.

Miyake and group³¹ have demonstrated to the first example of an optically active π -configuration poly-(azomethine) derivative exhibiting supramolecular self assembled nanofibrous structure (Scheme 13).

Scheme 13

Conclusion

The importance of azomethine ylide chemistry has witnessed an exponential increase as a tool for constructing the nitrogen containing five-membered heterocycles which are core structural motifs of numerous natural products and different biologically relevant compounds.

Acknowledgement

Financial support from UGC, CSIR and BRNS (DAE) is gratefully acknowledged

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